

Weak Measurements and Conditional Probabilities of Bound Systems

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Weak measurements are currently used to directly measure wavefunctions (1),(2). In this note, we compare the formalism of weak measurements with that of conditional probabilities $P(p/x)$ arguing that such probabilities may also be directly measured and follow directly from the weak measurement formalism. This seems to be a shift in thinking from the approach of formulating quantum relationships in terms of the spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$ and $a^*(p)a(p)$ used in the Heisenberg uncertainty relationship and Ehrenfest's relationships.

Weak Measurements

Weak measurements provide one way to measure a wavefunction directly (1). The formalism makes use of a double measurement on a system $|W_i\rangle$, i.e. first a weak one using the operator A , followed by a strong measurement i.e a projection onto a final state $\langle c|$. The measurement of A i.e. $|a\rangle\langle a|$ is weak in the sense it does not disturb the quantum system. Given that W_i and $|c\rangle$ deal with probability measures and not with actual stochastic motion of a quantum particle, it seems one performs many measurements over an ensemble.

$$\langle A \text{ weak} \rangle = \frac{\langle c|a\rangle\langle a|W_i\rangle}{\langle c|W_i\rangle} \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{If } \langle c| = \langle p| \text{ and } \langle a| = \langle x| \text{ one has: } \langle A \text{ weak} \rangle = \frac{\exp(ipx) W(x)}{a(p)} \quad ((2a))$$

Using $p=0$, yields $\langle A \text{ weak} \rangle = W(x)/a(0)$ where $a(0)$ is a constant.

In (1), measurements of photon's wavefunction have been carried out using this process.

In general, $\langle A \text{ weak} \rangle$ is a complex entity i.e. $W(x)$ is complex for a non-bound system. In (2), a formalism describing the effect of a weak measurement on the measurement system is developed. It is assumed there is an interaction between the system $|W_i\rangle$ and the measurement system $|W_m\rangle$ of $\text{Hint} = g \delta(t-t_0) A p$ where A is the weak operator on W_i and p the momentum operator on W_m . The interaction is used in the evolution operator $\exp(i t \text{Hint})$ which acts on $|W_i\rangle|W_m\rangle$. Expanding the interaction operator and keeping the first order term yields:

$$|q\rangle = (1 - i \langle W_f|W_i\rangle A w p |W_m\rangle) \quad (\text{from (2)}) \quad \text{where } p = -i d/dx \quad ((2b)) \quad A w = \langle W_f A W_i \rangle / \langle W_f W_i \rangle$$

In (2), it is shown full detail that the real part of $A w = a + ib$ (e.g. $W(x)$) shifts the x part of $|W_m\rangle$ by an amount proportional to $\text{Real}(A w)$ and the complex part the momentum by a term proportional to $\text{Im}(A w)$ i.e.

$$\langle x \text{ measuring device} \rangle_f = \langle x \rangle_i + g a + g b m \frac{d}{dt} \{\text{Var}(x)\} \text{Var}(x)$$

This result follows directly from ((2b)) if one keeps terms of order g when calculating q^*q . $|q\rangle$ is written as: $\text{Re} \exp(iS)$ with the time-dependent Schrodinger equation: $i\hbar d|q\rangle/dt = -1/2m d/dx d/dx |q\rangle + V(x)|q\rangle$. The imaginary part is taken so $V(x)$ is not used. Details are given in (2) and are not repeated here. (The calculation involves a kind of continuity type equation when the imaginary part is taken.)

And $\langle p \text{ measure} \rangle f = \langle p \rangle + 2gb \text{ Var}(p)$ where b is the imaginary part of A_w .

$\langle x_i \rangle = \langle W_{m0} x W_{m0} \rangle$ $\langle x_f \rangle = \langle q x q \rangle / \langle q | q \rangle$ and $\text{Var}(x) \text{Var}(x) = \langle W_{m0} x x W_{m0} \rangle - \langle W_{m0} x W_{m0} \rangle \langle W_{m0} x W_{m0} \rangle$ etc.

Thus, one may measure both real and complex parts of a system (e.g. $W(x)$) during a weak measurement.

Conditional Probabilities

Quantum mechanics seems to traditionally focus on the full probabilities $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$. These are used to calculate variances in the Heisenberg uncertainty relationship $\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar/2$ and also in Ehrenfest's theorem linking quantum averages to a kind of Newton's law. Thus, the idea seems to be that should integrate over all x to obtain quantum relationships. We argue that like in classical physics, relationships such as energy conservation should exist at each x point. We further argue that a momentum distribution is established at each point x . It is interesting to note that because actual particle motion is stochastic, the distribution at each x has to be measured over time and during these measurements, one may obtain information about the momentum distribution at all x points.

In a number of previous notes, we described quantum bound states as being based on conditional probability. In other words, a stochastic potential $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V(k) \exp(ikx)$ yields hits of momentum k at x at different times, leading to a momentum distribution at x given by:

$$P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x) \quad ((3))$$

Here, $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ is the wavefunction.

$P(p/x)$ is directly related to an important physical condition at each point x :

$$[\text{Sum over } p p^2/2m a(p) \exp(ipx)] / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((4))$$

The idea of classical conservation of energy at each point x is argued to hold on average at each point x in quantum mechanics. In addition, there seems to be an artificial time associated with vrms as one moves from one x to another. In reality, the particle is stochastic, it seems, and

receives stochastic hits moving it from one place to another, but ((4)) describes probability averages.

A question, however, is whether ((1)) may be measured. We try to argue it is linked to the weak measurement approach.

If one applies the quantum time-dependent equation to a bound state, a factor of $\exp(-iEt)$ appears where E is the average energy of the bound state. From ((3)), the factor $\exp(ipx)$ may be combined with $\exp(-iEt)$ to form a “wave like” relative conditional probability term: $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ where the same E holds for all p . This is unusual as the phase velocity is given by E/p . For large p , E/p is small and vice versa. In fact, E/p seems to be related to the classical energy density at each x given by $E/v(x)$. In the quantum large energy limit, one p dominates each x point. Then, mE/p is the energy density related to p .

“ t ” seems to be a kind of ensemble time with bound state energy representing periodicity in time just as $\exp(ipx)$ represents periodicity in space. $\exp(ipx)$ leads to physical observations in the spatial density $W(x)W(x)$ while $\exp(iEt)\exp(-iEt)$ cancel from the spatial density. It does not, however, cancel from the relative conditional probability $a(p)\exp(ipx)\exp(-iEt)$. In time-dependent quantum mechanics, the various $\exp(-iE_jt)$ factors for E_j energies do not cancel and lead to physical effects just as $\exp(ipx)$ values do. Nevertheless, a single $\exp(ipx)$ receives a phase which may be observable in slit experiments. Thus, $\exp(-iEt)$ should also be physical and is sometimes used to measure a phase received by a free quantum particle, e.g. if energy is shifted by a perturbation for example.

It seems quantum mechanics deals with relative probabilities of the form $\exp(+/- i p x)$ or $\exp(-i E t)$ provided there exist constant averages. These may be related to d/dx and d/dt as well as to other factors such as average kinetic energy. (One may have a momentum distribution at a certain point leading to a kinetic energy at x and may consider a translation (d/dx) to determine how the average changes.) For a single particle bound state, there exists an average E value constant at each x , so $\exp(iE_{ave}t)$ appears. Average kinetic energy is usually a function of x , so an $\exp(i p x)$ probability results at a lower level i.e. the level of a possible momentum value. Consider the case of a particle moving in a box with an infinite potential at the walls. All p states are stirred up at the wall so there is an $\exp(ipx)$ for each, but at each x in the interior the average kinetic energy is equal, thus one expects a form $\exp(-i p_{ave} x)$. Given that there is forward and backward motion: $W(x) = -i^{1/2} (\exp(ip_{ave} x) - \exp(-ip_{ave} x))$.

Conditional Probabilities and Weak Measurements

In (1), the weak measurement approach is used to weakly measure the position of photons, followed by a strong measurement which filters out photons with a momentum of zero. Thus, ((1)) becomes:

$$\langle p \rangle_{\text{weak}} = \langle p|x \rangle \langle x|W \rangle / \langle p|W \rangle = \exp(ipx) W(x) / a(p) \quad ((5))$$

For $p=0$, one has: $W(x)/a(0)$ where $a(0)$ is a constant. Thus, one may directly measure the wavefunction as done in (1).

If instead one performs a weak measurement of momentum $|p\rangle\langle p|$, followed by a strong of position, the formalism yields:

$$\langle x \rangle_{\text{weak}} = \langle x|p \rangle \langle p|W \rangle / \langle x|W \rangle = \exp(-ipx) a(p) / W(x) \quad ((6))$$

If $a(p)=\pm a(-p)$ ((6)) essentially becomes ((3)), the conditional probability $P(p/x)$. Thus, it seems conditional probability is linked to the formalism of weak measurements. The fact that one may measure the wavefunction $W(x)$ directly already implies that the conditional probability ((6)) is measurable.

One may inquire about stochastic hits from $V(x)$ between the weak and strong measurements. A quantum particle moves in a stochastic manner due to stochastic hits from a potential. It may be at x_1 with p_1 at t_1 and then receive a new momentum p_2 moving it to x_2 at t_2 . Then, it may be hit backwards etc. The probability formalism of quantum mechanics, however, does not follow this direct physical motion, but rather seems to provide probabilities for the particle to be at a point x with momentum p . This is directly related to the wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and it seems $W(x)$ is a fundamental object of quantum mechanics. The stochastic hits delivered by $V(x) = \sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$ are already incorporated in the establishment of $P(p/x)$ which is an average. In other words, one seems to be treating the measuring system and well as the quantum system in terms of probability averages (at each x), rather than considering an actual stochastic trajectory of a quantum particle. Thus, it seems one need not worry about stochastic hits between measurements. Many measurements, however, are needed to establish these averages. The concern is that the weak measurement does not upset the quantum bound system.

Weak Measurements and Photon Absorption

It is interesting to compare the time-dependent Schrodinger equation formalism of a weak measurement with photon absorption i.e. product wavefunctions in a time independent Schrodinger formalism. In the weak measurement, (2) describes an interaction Hamilton between the system and measuring device of $H_{int} = g \delta(t-t_0) A p$ where g is a constant, A the weak operator acting on the system and p the momentum operator acting on the measurement system. H_{int} acts on the product wavefunction $|Ws\rangle|Wm\rangle$ where s denotes system and m the measuring system. It is interesting to note that $|Ws\rangle$ is produced by a quantum particle interacting with a potential $V(x)$ in the bound case scenario. The measuring system, during a weak measurement, apparently does not upset the system resonance and so interacts with Ws of the system. This is a product wavefunction scenario, where a time dependent Schrodinger equation is used because the system and measuring system will not form a new resonance.

One may compare this with a resonance system (e.g. single electron atom) absorbing a photon. W_0 represents (e.g.) the ground state of an electron in resonance in a potential. A photon is absorbed and it seems to act somewhat like a measuring system. It does not directly interact with the potential, but indirectly and a new overall resonance is formed so the time independent Schrodinger equation is used. In such a case, one may use a product wavefunction $W_0 W_1$ where W_1 is related to the photon. Then: $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} (W_0 W_1) + V(x) W_0 W_1 = (E_0 + E_1) W_0 W_1$. One may decouple to obtain an equation showing an interaction between the photon and W_0 :

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_1 - \frac{1}{m} \frac{dW_0}{dx} / W_0 \frac{dW_1}{dx} = E_1 W_1 \quad ((7))$$

This seems to be somewhat related to the idea of coupling a system state W_0 with a measurement state W_1 . For the system interacting weakly with the measurement system, one may use the evolution operator $\exp(i t H_{int}) W_0 W_1$ and not the full Schrodinger equation. One sees in ((7)) that the average momentum of the system W_0 i.e. $\frac{dW_0}{dx} / W_0$ affects the measurement system (photon) W_1 .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the weak measurement formalism established for the measure of the wavefunction, i.e. a weak measurement of x followed by a strong of p if switched to p followed by x yields the formula for the conditional probability $P(p/x)$ if $a(p) = \pm a(-p)$ which we have used in a number of notes. Thus, the $P(p/x)$ formalism which may be used to establish average conservation of energy at each point x , just as in classical physics, is linked to measurables. Traditionally, quantum mechanical measurables were associated with spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$ and not the wavefunction alone, discouraging perhaps the use of conditional probabilities.

References

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